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Truth, Transformation, and Transgender Identity: A Study of Laxmi Narayan Tripathi's *Red Lipstick: The Men in My Life*

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Abstract:

This paper critically explores the complex interplay of the truth, transformation, and transgender identity in *Red Lipstick: The Men in My Life (2016)*, by Laxmi Narayan Tripathi. This paper examines how Tripathi navigates personal and public spaces to assert agency, authenticity, and visibility as a transgender individual in a society deeply rooted in patriarchy and heteronormativity society with the lens of queer theory and gender performativity. Tripathi's memoir is a narrative of self-discovery but a radical political act that challenges the dominant discourses around gender, sexuality, and respectability. By projecting a specific proof in the form of personal truths – childhood experiences, relationships, and activism – Tripathi redefines the transformation not just as a physical or emotional journey, but as a socio-political stance against marginalisation. This study investigates how Laxmi Narayan Tripathi's *Red Lipstick: The Men in My Life (2016)* challenges traditional understandings of Gender, Kinship and Identity in India, exploring how life-writing becomes a political act of resistance and a tool for redefining transgender experiences. This paper draws upon theoretical frameworks of Judith Butler and

Susan Stryker to analyse how Tripathi's lived experience interrogates normative understandings of gender identity and the production of the truth. Through textual analysis and socio-cultural contextualization, this study will highlight how the text *Red Lipstick: The Men in My Life* (2016) has become a site of resistance that amplifies voices often silenced and marginalised. This paper argues that, Tripathi's narrative dismantles rigid binaries of male/female and normative/othered, offering a powerful testament to the politics of becoming and belonging in contemporary India.

Keywords: Laxmi Narayan Tripathi, transgender identity, Red Lipstick, queer theory, gender performativity, transformation, truth, autobiography, resistance, Indian LGBTQ+ rights.

Introduction

The transgender community in India, despite its ancient roots and spiritual legacy, has long faced social marginalisation, legal invisibility, and social discrimination. However, the past two decades have witnessed a revolutionary shift led by bold and unapologetic voices within the community. India is currently experiencing a significant shift, as conversations around transgender identities move from silence and invisibility toward open acknowledgement and acceptance. This transformation is vividly captured in Laxmi Narayan Tripathi's *Red Lipstick: The Men in My Life* (2016), where she recounts her tremendous yet challenging journey of physical, and mental transformation. From being a 'he' to a 'she', from being a man physically to a woman at core, and later as a complete transwoman individual. In recent decades, the discourse surrounding gender identity and the politics of representation has gained critical momentum, especially in postcolonial societies grappling with intersectional realities. Among the influential voices that have emerged from the transgender community in

India is Laxmi Narayan Tripathi – an activist for the community. She is a dancer, a spiritual leader, and a writer and her autobiography *Red Lipstick: The Men in My Life (2016)*, offers a compelling narrative of personal truth, transformation, and self-assertion. Born in a traditional Brahmin family and assigned male at birth, Laxmi’s life journey defies societal norms and showcases a vibrant redefinition of gender and selfhood. By writing her autobiography, she has tried to reconstruct her identity, which the rigid heteronormative culture has provided not in its completeness but in fragments. *Red Lipstick* is not merely a personal memoir; it is a political account that challenges the dominant narratives about the transgender experience in India. Laxmi blends emotional vulnerability with unflinching boldness as she recounts episodes of abuse, love, marginalisation, and activism. Her narrative resists victimhood and instead foregrounds agency, self-fashioning, and transformation – physically, emotionally, and socially. The autobiography becomes a site of resistance, in which the body is both the text and the terrain of struggle and celebration. This paper aims to construct a strong analysis of transgender identity by exploring the interconnection among the themes of truth, transformation, and self-representation. It argues that Laxmi’s life-writing challenges traditional understandings of genders and emphasises the fluidity of identity and power through personal narrative by relying on gender and queer theories. Particularly to the works of Judith Butler and Susan Stryker, the paper also critically examines how Laxmi’s articulation of selfhood transcends both biological essentialism and cultural marginalisation. In doing so, the study situates *Red Lipstick* within a broader literary and socio-political context of transgender visibility and empowerment in contemporary India.

Theoretical Framework

To make the arguments in contexts and make them clear to readers, this paper draws upon the theoretical frameworks of Judith Butler’s concept of Gender Performativity from

Gender Trouble: Feminism and the Subversion of Identity (1990) and Susan Stryker works *Transgender History* (2008) and Arvind Narrain's '*Because I have a Voice: Queer Politics in India* (2005)'. Judith Butler has conceptualised gender identity not as a fixed inherent essence, but a socially regulated construct. In her influential work *Gender Trouble* (1990), Butler writes, "There is no gender identity behind the expressions of gender; that identity is performatively constituted by the very 'expressions' that are said to be its results" (Butler 33). This idea is fundamental to understanding Laxmi's selfhood which does not emerge from a pre-determined gendered idea but is adopted and redefined through her daily choices, relationships, and public life. Laxmi's performance as a hijra, as a dancer, as a spiritual leader of Kinnar Akhada, and as an activist challenge the heteronormative society and asserts identity as a lived, performative truth. Closely tied to Butler's notion of performativity – that gender is not something one is, but something one does, repeatedly. In the context of *Red Lipstick*, Laxmi's performative acts – such as dressing in sarees, applying red lipstick, and wearing a large red bindi on her forehead, or engaging in ritual and public speaking – are not superficial but foundational to her self-definition. These acts resist marginalization and embody her claim to visibility and dignity. In her essay "My Words to Victor Frankenstein Above the Village of Chamounix," Susan Stryker writes, "I am a transsexual, and therefore I am a monster... But I am also the vehicle of a monstrous truth" (Stryker 240). This "monstrous truth" resembles Laxmi's unapologetic self-narration in *Red Lipstick* and also the way she has neither sanitized nor simplified her identity for mainstream acceptance, but instead presents her truth with boldness and emotional honesty. The very act of writing her autobiography – particularly her candid accounts of relationships with men – becomes transformative both personally and politically. Arvind Narrain, in *Queer: Despised Sexuality, Law and Social Change* (2004), emphasises that "Queer identities in India are not simply about sexuality or gender; they are about resistance to oppression, about challenging power structures that marginalise" (Narrain 88). Through this theoretical lens, *Red*

Lipstick can be interpreted as a text that constructs and asserts transgender identity through truth-telling, performance, and ongoing transformation. These concepts form the foundation of this research paper's analysis of Laxmi Narayan Tripathi's life-writing.

Evolution of the transgender community in India

The word spiritual may sound religious and orthodox at its core, but here it refers to how one's inner self shapes how we perceive and accept our physical appearances. That is how the lives of transgender individuals changed through a challenging process, which did not happen overnight but took many months and years to free them from trauma and pain, all in the quest to find the true nature of their body, mind, and soul. The journey of the transformation for any transgender person is not like walking on rose petals but like sitting on a throne of thorns – outwardly embodying feminine beauty while hiding the ugly pain reflected through their body. Talking about the physical appearance of the transgender individuals – often perceived as a problem – they are just like any other normal human being. There seems nothing, abnormal despite heteronormative societies often claiming that all queer people, effeminate boys, or masculine girls are abnormal. However after close observation, it gets clear that there is nothing wrong with the transgender individuals and even if there is something wrong apparently with the transgender individuals then surely, it is not them but actually to those who are observing them, and the people or communities who are looking at them with the perspective of something else, something other than the standard lens through which any other normal human beings are looked at. The whole idea of observation is based on sexual orientation of transgender individuals, even though sexual orientation has little connection with psychology; this applies not only to queer individuals but to all people. Here lies the struggle between fate and destiny. I quote lines from *Red Lipstick* that Laxmi said to the writer, who recorded then in the writer's note section of the text. 'Taqdeer upar wala deta hai, apni tadbeer se apni taqdeer ko badalna

padta hai. You're destined to do things but you do need to create your own opportunities'. (Tripathi 120).

Look into the brief history of homosexuality in India, they have a glorious, strong and evident history in our Indian culture however the same sex like Gay, Lesbian and Bisexuals and Gender specific Transgenders documentations are available in every form either it is in the letter or paintings, sculpturers and ancient monuments inscriptions we do have proper authentic proof to prove their existence in our culture. This research paper aims to show the changing phase of transgender in 21st century India. Transgender individuals are now considered the third gender because they represent an entire community whose visible sexuality is expressed physically and spiritually, and they have established their identity in modern Indian society.

Transgender Identity through Laxmi Narayan's Lens

Laxmi Narayan Tripathi's *Red Lipstick: The Men in My Life (2016)* chronicles not just the personal evolution of one transgender individual, but also mirrors the collective journey of the transgender community in India – a journey marked by trauma, transformation, resistance, and self-assertion. The narrative, woven through episodes of vulnerability and power, becomes a lens through which the multifaceted realities of Indian transgender lives are viewed. It is a journey from truth-telling, through transformational selfhood, toward the formation of a powerful transgender identity and representation that defies cultural invisibility.

Truth and Narrative Voice: The Autobiographical Act as Resistance

In the border protest against heteronormative society, Laxmi appears as an activist, and her team and organization played a pivotal role in the decriminalisation of homosexuality in India. In her autobiography *Red Lipstick: The Men in My Life (2016)*, she provides detailed

information about the campaign about the people and about the person who had helped her throughout the journey from becoming MAN to WOMAN – a Hijra. Laxmi’s confessional identity and voice are raw, as seen in her memoir where she writes, “I was born in a male body, but my soul was always feminine” (Tripathi 3). This early declaration sets the tone for a truth that does not seek validation but demands to be witnessed, which is why her voice seems unapologetic even as it recalls the traumatic experiences such as sexual abuse, betrayal, and professional discrimination. Her use of the first-person perspective is not merely stylistic but political. In a society that constantly speaks about hijras, Laxmi insists on speaking for herself. As Judith Butler theorises, “Gender is not something that one is, it is something one does, an act... a doing” (Butler 34). *Transformation and Selfhood: Performing Identity Beyond the Binary* – “Each time I danced, I was Laxmi, not the boy my family wanted me to be. I felt complete” (Tripathi 28), she writes. Whenever she danced for herself not as a performance but an emancipation. It is through Bharatanatyam and Kathak that Laxmi reclaims her femininity, asserting what Susan Stryker calls “the monstrous truth” of transgender embodiment. (Stryker 240). Transformation also involves leadership and activism. Similarly, Butler’s affirmation of *Queer Kinship* is that homosexuals and gender-nonconforming individuals can form valid kinship structures, including families, parenting roles, and intimate relationships that defy heterosexual norms. She writes: “The presumption that a child requires a ‘mother and a father’... is based on a naturalised and regulatory fiction.” (Butler, *Undoing Gender*, 104.) This directly supports the idea that transgender individuals like Laxmi can authentically inhabit motherhood, regardless of biological sex or reproductive capacity. Society assigns gender roles (e.g., “a mother nurtures, a father protects”), but Butler dismantles these assumptions by showing they are performative, not essential. As the first transgender person to represent Asia Pacific at the United Nations and the founder of the religious Kinnar Akhada, Laxmi reconstructs identity on her terms. She says, “People asked how a hijra could be spiritual. But I told them, the divine is

genderless” (Tripathi 162). Beneath her activist and assertive public persona, Laxmi reveals a deeply nurturing, feminine side wanting to embrace the purest form of being a woman. She embraces motherhood by adopting a child, Deepak Salvi in his teenage years, who has now grown into a man and married. She stated clearly that she wants to be a mother, and which is why she adopted Deepak as her son. Here she states, ‘I have wanted to be a mother ever since I was a child myself. If there is one emotion, I knew I wanted to fully understand and experience, it was of motherhood... I was ready to feel the giving and nurturing side of womanhood and so, even though I was very young, I felt I was ready to be a mother. And when the opportunity arose, I took it’ (Tripathi 43). Tripathi's maternal instincts defy conventional gender roles, which often restrict the notion of motherhood to cisgender women. By embracing motherhood through adoption, she reclaims a traditionally feminine role in a way that is inclusive and expansive. Her choice illustrates that parenting is not confined to biological capability but is grounded in emotional readiness and care ethics. This move challenges both heteronormative family models and societal perceptions of parental legitimacy, offering a counter-narrative to the belief that only cisgender individuals can provide a nurturing home.

In addition to this, Tripathi’s decision to adopt a teenager, rather than a young child, reflects a conscious understanding of the socio-legal landscape for queer individuals in India. Adoption laws and social attitudes often exclude or stigmatise transgender individuals, particularly in the context of family-building. By successfully adopting and parenting Deepak, Tripathi not only exercises her right to familial life but also paves the way for others in the queer community to imagine alternative kinship structures. Her lived experience broadens the scope of queer parenthood, portraying it as an act of love, responsibility, and defiance against restrictive norms. The act itself becomes a transformative social statement redefining who is allowed to nurture, care for, and raise the next generation in Indian society.

Transgender Identity and Representation: The Power of Self-Narration

Laxmi's identity is not defined solely by her transition or her struggle – it is an intersectional identity shaped by caste, class, performance, queerness, and spirituality. Her life resists the simplified image of the transgender person as either victim or spectacle. She embraces contradictions: “I’ve been a bar dancer, a sex worker, a UN speaker, a hijra guru. I am all of these and none of these” (Tripathi 190). This complexity counters the media's often sensationalist portrayal of transgender lives. In contrast to being passively represented, Laxmi reclaims authorship: “My story is not about becoming a woman. It's about being Laxmi” (Tripathi 195). Her self-narration echoes Arvind Narrain's argument that “queer identities in India are a form of resistance to systems that seek to discipline desire and selfhood” (Narrain 88).

Conclusion

The Transgender community in India is undergoing significant change. After gaining visibility and employment opportunities, many transgender individuals want to experience all aspects of womanhood, rather than limiting themselves solely to activism or navigating the complexities of power and politics. Though the basic aim of each queer individual is first to gain his/her identity in the community and then to earn respect and a better life, such a complete phase of life is still the dream of many trans individuals like her; however, their dedication to the welfare of the community remains strong. She embraces her feminine identity while drawing strength from the resilience she developed during her time navigating a masculine world to stand still for their community. She is an inspiration to nearly every gender non-conforming individual. She is not only limited the hijra community but also raises her voice against the discrimination towards Gay, Lesbian and bisexual. Her journey offers hope the lives of all transgender

individuals could improve if they receive support from their family, society, and government; with such support they can contribute meaningfully to the society, much as they did in the past. In India, change is increasingly visible within the hijra community. They seek education and employment for a better future, aspiring beyond traditional roles such as sex work, performing 'Badhaai' ceremonies, or relying on begging. They want more from society and the world.

Works Cited:

Abrams, M. H., and Geoffrey Galt Harpham. *A Glossary of Literary Terms*. 11th ed, Cengage Learning, 2015.

Biswas, Anamika, and Nandin Soora. "Education of Transgenders in India: Status and Challenges." *International Journal of Law Management & Humanities*, vol. 4, no. 5, 2021, pp. 415–430.

Bolich, G. G. *Transgender History and Geography: Crossdressing in Context*. Vol. 3, Psyche's Press, 2010.

Butler, Judith. *Bodies That Matter: On the Discursive Limits of Sex*. Routledge, 2011.

Butler, Judith. *Gender Trouble: Feminism and the Subversion of Identity*. Routledge, 1990.

Butler, Judith. "Performative Acts and Gender Constitution: An Essay in Phenomenology and Feminist Theory." *Theatre Journal*, vol. 40, no. 4, Dec. 1988, pp. 519–531. Johns Hopkins University Press.

Butler, Judith. *Undoing Gender*. Routledge, 2004.

Narrain, Arvind, and Gautam Bhan, editors. *Because I Have a Voice: Queer Politics in India*. Yoda Press, 2005.

Narrain, Arvind. *Queer: Despised Sexuality, Law and Social Change*. Yoda Press, 2004.

Stryker, Susan. *Transgender History*. Seal Press, 2008.

Stryker, Susan. "My Words to Victor Frankenstein Above the Village of Chamounix:

Performing Transgender Rage." *GLQ: A Journal of Lesbian and Gay Studies*, vol. 1, no. 3, 1994, pp. 237–254.

Tripathi, Laxmi Narayan. *Red Lipstick: The Men in My Life*. Penguin Books, 2016.